

ECONOMIC POLICY AND MANAGEMENT STYLE OF GENGHIS KHAN

*Dorj T.,
Alimaa D.,
Dash D.*

Abstract

In this article the authors analyze economic policy and management style of Genghis Khan. The Mongolian ruler created a brand new economic model for Mongolia and introduced legislation that promoted economic development and progress. Genghis Khan used meritocracy in recruitment of his lieutenants and created a unique single economic space in Eurasia long before supranational organizations like WTO came into existence. Nowadays elements of Genghis Khan's rule have been introduced into contemporary management theory. They are used for management of successful companies.

Keywords: economic policy, the Mongol Empire, economic globalization, state management, meritocracy, centralization, decentralization.

In the year 2006 Mongolia and the rest of the world jubilantly celebrated the 800th anniversary of foundation of the Great Mongol Empire. Within the context of this event I studied, as much as I could, state economic policy and ruling management style of the Great Mongol Empire. It is my privilege to share and discuss my opinions on this topic with scientists and scholars of other countries. And here lies the main goal of my work, which consists of two parts.

1. Economic policy of Genghis Khan

The economic policy of Genghis Khan aimed at assurance of statehood and political independence of Mongolia. Its goal was to prevent economic dependence, unveil and eliminate any signs of it and guarantee self-determination of the national economy.

Genghis Khan introduced a new system of labor division into herdsmen, shepherds, cattlemen, and milkmaids in the nomadic husbandry.

Such labor division gave its own fruits. Scholars and researchers agree that this labor division gave respective names to the administrative divisions such as khushuuns, and also to the ethnic divisions such as tribes, so that these established traditions lasted for centuries. Polls by the American "Washington Post" proclaimed Genghis Khan as the Man of the Second Millennium, the most outstanding figure of the epoch. This demonstrates once again that he was truly a master of economics.

According to the newspaper article Genghis Khan and his successors created a free trade zone that encompassed most of the Eurasian continent, promoting and expanding cultural and civilizational ties between East and West. Seven centuries before the Internet Genghis Khan and his successors, for the first time ever in human history created a worldwide network of international relations and communications of a single state with the rest of the then known world.

Structure of the economic policy by Genghis Khan is defined in the following manner:

- Development strategy of animal husbandry
- Security of nature and environmental protection
- Expansion of internal and external trade
- Development of economic infrastructure
- Control and maintenance of state financial and taxation system

- Use of traditional knowledge and skills of ordinary intelligent people for technical progress and technological achievements in manufacturing industry.

Since the creation of the unified Great Mongol Empire land use was an indispensable part of the state policy. The country's independence and its economic development, customs and lifestyle of the people, nature protection all were taken as one large complex method [14]. At that time Genghis Khan was a sole ruler and land ownership was organized in the following way:

1. State land ownership was under the control of Genghis Khan. Some lands were owned by his officers - chiefs of one thousand warriors, who made up an administrative unit.

2. Protected lands / settlements named "INJ" belonged to the natives of various tribes to whom Genghis Khan granted rights of timeless ownership.

3. Premium land: these lands were granted by Genghis Khan to princes, army commanders and others for their distinguished services to him and the country.

These lands were called "TUSHEE", literally meaning 'rely' or 'support'.

Doctor of Economics D. Lhashid wrote: "From Genghis Khan to Ligden Khan (meaning: ray of light, saint) more than thirty-seven khans sat on the throne. Amongst them Ugedei was the shrewdest and left much greater legacy to his descendants." Therefore we must agree that the achievements of Ugedei were fruits of his natural qualities. Under Ugedei manufacturing grew at the cost of his own gratuity. Besides the production of weapons, armors, sabers, bows and arrows, many people toiled to make war goods. He also focused on household and bull-pull carts manufacturing. In Kharkhorin, the imperial capital of Mongolia, steel production was operating. It is said that Ugedei built many carpentry workshops, where around 200.000 foreign carpenters and builders worked. Khan's wise taxation policy had an enormous effect on the empire's economic advance. In 1229 he introduced a new State Treasure House Tax Law and set the tax limits and its collection procedures for livestock husbandry and agriculture. Above all he held a thorough census of conquered lands and foreign population within the empire, and accordingly collected due taxes and reassured their submission. In 1233 he made several changes in

taxation law, according to which one head of livestock (horse, cow, and sheep) per one hundred ought to be given to state as a part of tax. Also taxation system on trade was revised and considerably severed. The following regulations were established: Salt Tax Law in 1230, Trade Tax Law in 1234, and Silk Goods Tax Law in 1236. Besides special international taxation rules were introduced for influential foreign traders and merchants. In 1236 by Ugedei's decree for the first time in world history paper money went into circulation.

A world renowned Mongolian horse-relay service - "urtou" (meaning: post), which operated in distance of every 30-40 kilometers, had following three types: long, medium and short distance ones. Its service named "yam" was fast, effective and safe, because it was constantly guarded by the Mongolian cavalry units.

Paying due attention to the development of national economy and understanding that it had by now a serious impact on the expansion of international trade, Genghis Khan took dramatic actions, which had world significance.

Using classic economic language, serf-herders, for instance, paid their rents in-kind because there were no rents and taxes that could be paid with money. Famous Mongolian historian D. Gongor writes in his volume one of "Chronicles of the Khalkha Mongols" that ministry held an annual head-count of horses and livestock and thoroughly registered all details of increase or decrease in livestock and necessary measurements to tackle any problems. Only the Khan alone knew the true statistical figures on horses, which were not only used for labor, but had strategic importance too.

Therefore, amongst the traditional five types of livestock the Mongols had, horses were more important to the state.

Carpentry and manufacturing played an additional role in the Mongolian economy. From times immemorial the Mongols made their own weapons, jewelry and household goods from bone, hide, bronze, iron, gold, and stone.

Ugedei Khan constantly took care of the Mongolian Empire's economy and continued political modernization, which Genghis Khan set in motion. In 1231 Ugedei founded a Ministry of Internal Chancellery and appointed Yelui-Chu-tzai, his father's closely entrusted man, its minister. In the same year he decreed the separation of the military administration affairs from civil affairs. In this manner chiefs of ten thousands became responsible for military affairs and specially assigned clerks for civil affairs such as collection of taxes and foreign intelligence. These actions signified a new dawn of ruling and management style where military and civil matters were strongly defined and separated.

During Ugedei's reign a unified monetary and financial policy within the whole empire was carried out for the first time. On top of that, modernization of tax and credit policy was accomplished. In 1233-1236 a new population census was held throughout the empire. Merchants and traders were no longer allowed to lend money at high interest rates as they did before.

Generally speaking, Ugedei Khan enriched the modernized state policy with his brilliantly effective economic policy. From this time the great empire that

Genghis Khan created on horseback began to be ruled off horseback by Ugedei Khan.

2. Distinguished features of Mongolian administration and management in the reign of Genghis Khan

For the Mongols it was natural to strictly follow their laws and be taught to run their households, conduct military affairs, prophesy religion and belief in order to evolve their world view, and to observe their customs and traditions. In the process of their daily life, specific forms of administrative methods were developed and they were inherited for centuries. Probably the greatest work on Mongolian history «Wisdom of the Great Proclamation of Statecraft- Ikh Yasa» can be called an encyclopedia of the theoretical mentality of Mongolian management. Rise, fall and resurrection of our ancestors of 4000-5000 years BC are inscribed in this chronicle, and it encompasses all spheres of law, culture, social life and origin of the Mongols.

If we go deeper into the historical past of the Mongols, we will find out that numerous gifted and outstanding figures like Great Khans and scholars were born in the Mongolian nomadic world. Renowned Russian scientist L. N. Gumilyov noted, "From the point of biological formation Mongolia is embossed with nature-climate environment and in these geo-ecological conditions stronger and wiser people are born than in any other nations." This conclusion itself turns out to be a vital factor of unveiling the traditions and distinctions of Mongolian administration. In the "Wisdom of the Great Proclamation", the ideals of which Genghis Khan implemented in the Mongolian society, the administration strategy is described as a symbol of control over the human mind, of tribal management and of social organization in decimal systems, as well as regulation of human activities prompted by traditional folklore, proverbs and tales. This certain system and its distinctive methods encompass all spheres of society. For example, it works to suit the scale of established traditions and lifestyle of certain administered group, in other words it doesn't infringe one's internal affairs and customs. Meanwhile, it allows swift unveiling of misdeeds and lays the right ways to correct them. On the state level of the Great Mongol Empire, "Wisdom of the Great Proclamation" was adopted as a compilation of Genghis Khan's laws "Ikh Yos" or "Ikh Zasag". In modern terminology the judges and executors were "managers". The administration doctrine lies in the activation of a socio-ecological system, which forms the foundation of execution of the wisdom. That wisdom is clear in the philosophy of the Mongolian society whereas the Mongols say: "at first amend yourself, then amend your family", which accordingly sets the right limits of building a prosperous and healthy family, and which, in its turn, becomes the core of the state's prosperity, successful economic development, and absolute society. In other words, it means that all family members forming the decimal system must possess good knowledge, skills, and bold life experience. Therefore, a terminology and a definition of statecraft invented by the Mongolian statecraft wisdom had a world significance, as G. Hegel wrote in his «Historical Philoso-

phy-National Criteria»: «History of humanity commences with the Mongols» and V. G. Vernadsky, a representative of Eurasianism concept, noted: «Two cores of the Great Russian Empire lie in nothing, but in the statecraft legacy of the Great Mongols and in the stately traditions of Byzantium».

Organizational structure of the Great Mongol Empire: Though historians consider that the Mongol administration methods originated in the Hun era, from the viewpoint of the modern management science, such methods were not firm enough. Huns also had the decimal system, which consisted of units of tens, hundreds and thousands, but they had purely military motivations and characteristics. In the final stages of creation of the Mongolian State /SHM-The Secret History of the Mongols 202/, with his decree Genghis Khan founded the first actively functioning military-political, social structure of Mongolia. Ultimate goal of that was to accomplish the "Wisdom of Great Proclamation of Statecraft". According to his decree tribal structure was abolished forever and the state was to be ruled by the Great Khan with the help of the council of his ninety-five lieutenants (commanders of 1000-men units) led by general Mukhulai. Also Genghis guaranteed his own personal security by setting up a guard squadron named kheshigten or elite troops. Genghis Khan chose the meritocracy as the best way to reward people for what they had accomplished for him and appointed those who fought for him to found a Unified Mongolian State/SHM224/ his commanders. Hundreds made up thousands and thousands made up tens of thousand. Such administration structure, on the one hand, was a constantly functioning system of state rule, and on the other hand, it administered social life of the country. And most important, it suited the nomadic society perfectly. From the viewpoint of contemporary management, this structure had its own distinctive characteristics such as high adaptability to the environment, less complicated structure and flexibility. It was also highly responsive to important decisions.

Obviously, every system has its own defining administrative parameters. Administrative criteria form one of such parameters. Genghis Khan developed nine criteria of administering. Nowadays the dominant view is "the higher the organizational standards of administering, the lower the criteria are." More and more research works in management tend to support it. But the administering criteria of the Great Mongol Empire, which dominated half of the world, consisted of nine main stages, if we use modern terminology. Genghis Khan himself ruled over nine commanders or military generals "urlug", and those generals, in their turn, ruled over nine commanders of 1000-men regiments and those nine commanders controlled nine centurions, while nine centurions ruled over nine 10-men squad commanders. In this way Genghis Khan's administration criteria were proportionally as 1:9 or nine men per one commander were assigned. Initially, based on such system of administration Genghis Khan successfully implemented his great administration strategy.

If we look at the organizational structure of Genghis Khan's state we will see that this proportion was 1:1 or, in other words, one chief or commander over

one subordinate. Therefore, a structural organization of administration by Genghis Khan is not just a compound of aligned units, but a thoroughly executed strategic organization of "unquestionable-direct-subordination". Apart from the aligned units there was a functional unit too. «The Secret History of the Mongols» confirms that «Ikh Khuraldai» - «Great Council» was the embodiment of a functional unit, which included advisors to Genghis Khan, for instance, shaman Teb-tengri (meant ascending to heaven), who was then the mediator communicating on behalf of Genghis Khan with the great eternal heav-en; four elite gallants "khulug baatar" and four army generals, who served as advisors to the commanders of 1000-men regiments. History tells us that Genghis Khan frequently listened carefully to their ideas before he made final decisions. "The Secret History of the Mongols" is replete with names of many historical figures who helped Genghis Khan with their discreet minds in reaching the ultimate solutions. One of them was Tatatunga, an educated and enlightened Uighur, as well as Yelui-Chu-Tzai, a shrewd and honest Kidan man. They all made their invaluable contributions into the fulfillment of Genghis Khan's strategy and he certainly greatly appreciated their talents and knew well that he could rely on them to organize truly professional administration.

Style and method of leadership of Genghis Khan: Genghis was brought up to become a leader since his early childhood. Among the Mongol khanlig or ethnic groups was one called Khiad Borjigin whose chieftain Esugei was a grandson of Khabul Khan, the strongest and most influential leader in his own time. Esugei taught young Temijin, his oldest son, to be a successor of his great ancestors. Frankly, he prepared his son to be a leader of his Golden Dynasty by the will of the Eternal Blue Sky. By the age of eighteen Temujin had already developed the following characteristics of a leader:

- Psychological traits of a future leader.
- Throughout his youth he sensed people's aspiration to live in peace and tranquility
- He understood and conveyed this idea to everyone that bloodshed is unavoidable to achieve peace.
- Real sense of environment and sharp intuition, as well as the ability to compensate for his shortcomings with the support of his close friends.
- He could discard vengeance and ally with his archenemies in order to achieve his goal.
- Genghis Khan could attract masses on his side in humane and benevolent ways.
- The ability to learn from other people's mistakes.
- He could listen to the words of his enemies make correct conclusions.
- He accepted the experiences and advices of intelligent and thoughtful elderly people.

These fundamental traits gradually accumulated in him and enriched his personality making Genghis Khan a truly outstanding leader. They led to his great victories, achievements and ultimate triumph.

As the oldest son or the orphaned family he had a strong psychological impact on his younger brothers since childhood. His lifetime companion and closest

friend Boorchii praised and hailed Genghis Khan's wisdom and compassion in "The Secret History of the Mongols". And it is not only an appraisal, it's also Boorchii's pledge to him and the readers can feel how much one's personal character and pattern can have such a magnifying effect on others. During the Great Khuraldai (Great Council), Genghis Khan's mastery in leadership was displayed even bolder.

Decisions made on the Great Khuraldai were kept as a top state secret until they are being carried out duly. A moral and spiritual strength which Genghis Khan possessed was always shown in his brilliant leadership.

Studies on Genghis Khan's leadership mastery by the American scholars: Style and method of leadership of Genghis Khan became nowadays a subject of study for the American businessmen. To give you some ideas on that, we bring to your attention some results of research work done by Mick Ache, an American franchiser and advisor to "Leader Valley Co." on leadership. He defines the style and method of Genghis Khan's leadership in the following manners:

- Ability to foresee any events - ENVISION
- Ability to execute anything he planned - ENABLE
- Possess all necessary resources and energy to achieve the goal - ENERGIZE
- Granting an authority to his subordinates - EMPOWER

1. Firstly, Genghis Khan had an incredible ability to predict and to foresight.

He foresighted that the wealth gained by conquest of foreign countries is a sole method to terminate the inter-tribal confrontations for wealth.

2. Secondly, Genghis Khan had an astute ability to execute his plans. We cannot say at all that he won wars with a weapon which his opponents did not possess. The only mystery of his military triumph lies in his magnificent utilization of military technology and his war machine in regards of the existed circumstances. Genghis Khan strengthened his army soldiers' will to fight by applying an iron discipline, rare military tactics and perfect administrative organization of his army. These abilities became the fundamental factors in creation of the Mongol Empire.

3. Thirdly, Genghis Khan was able to make his subordinates work wisely and effectively. He always knew well what his subordinates wanted and needed from him.

He elevated their interests ahead of his own. It also allowed avoiding the poverty in general. Therefore, Genghis Khan shared the war booty equally among his subordinates. They knew well that more victory meant more booty, and they did their best to gain it.

4. Fourthly, Genghis Khan granted a certain authority to his subordinates. Some might think what kind of an iron leader he was if he permitted an authority to his servants. But in reality he was a rarely gifted leader, who could delegate authority to his subordinates. In order to strengthen his power he appointed people to high ranking posts without taking into consideration their social origin. So, his meritocracy gave people enormous faith and belief in him.

Now I would like to draw your attention to a scheme by an American researcher Mick Ache on the administration methods of Genghis Khan:

Style and method of administration by Genghis Khan in modern Society

	In the Era of Genghis Khan	In the modern society
Conditions and circumstances at the time	Wide steppes of Mongolia and a war that engulfed the world	Period of common world market. Economic war without end
Era of Genghis Khan's wisdom	Reality Temp and Speed Power and Knowledge Compensation of power Struggle for the unity of sorrow and happiness Attempt for luck or Risk	Consider crisis as a factor of development Not to clinch to the old styles and out-off-date methods Ruling the dynamic economy Systematic style and creative organization Invigorate the faith between the two Search for a new style and an advanced method
Estimations given by the economic scientists of USA and Great Britain	-Highly Perfected Management-CEO -Foresight Aptitude-ENVISION -Execution Ability-ENABLE -Energy Possession-ENERGY -Power and Rights-EMPOWER	
Estimation by the public	Skillful ability of Mongolian businessmen to overcome the financial and economic obstacles with the involvement and assistance of World Bank and other donor states.	

Management strategy of Genghis Khan and its realization: A warring environment on the one hand and a constant inter-tribal confrontation on the other hand, was a condition in which Temujin's psychology of a leader and his personality with world envision were developed and formed. From the early childhood Temujin

firmly understood and constituted for himself that a source of country's prosperity laid in fraternal inter-tribal relations. Strategy of fraternity of inter-tribal relation in Mongolia was conceived by Genghis Khan in the following manners:

1. Firstly, compromise would lead to unification of all Mongol tribes under a sole ruler.
2. Secondly, it would secure military-political and social administration under one ruler.
3. Thirdly, it would create a common production system.

Internal Compromise /fraternity/: Internal peace among the Mongolian tribal population needed to be achieved under the ideals of Eternal Blue Sky and the Nine Sacred Banners "Suld" - a symbol of spirit of the Mongolian warriors. On top of that, reaching an inter-tribal compromise and expansion of its orbit were an indispensable part of Genghis Khan's strategy. The fundamental goal in this strategy was to achieve peaceful existence of the Mongolian people. And that was also feasible through a compromise. Therefore, it was essential, first of all, to reach a kind of inter-tribal compromise or to organize this campaign effectively and cautiously without disturbing the already fragile spiritual or inner layers of the people, and furthermore, to prioritize positive influence on the outside world too. This in the end would result in the creation of both internal and external peace for the Mongolian nation.

Achieving internal compromise and expanding external compromise were very difficult tasks which demanded enormous power and wisdom from Genghis Khan. A so called strategy "For the future deeds" created by Genghis Khan had become not only a postulate for stable world progress in the twenty-first century, but also a fundamental core of peaceful and affluent life for the future generation. And for the sake of that every nation needs a space to live. For every country, no matter if it is tiny or huge, there is a chance to develop if there is a strategy with perspectives.

In the process of executing his great strategies Genghis Khan had to use his mighty war machine while implementing new tactics and innovations of his time, and above all, as time passed he achieved a perfection of his administration methods.

"The Secret History of the Mongols" gives a clear description of that. For a while he befriended an enemy to extract what he needed to know or learn; sued for peace when it was required; avoided stronger opponents; weakened his opponents by making them fight each other; restrained himself from too much bloodshed; showed his compassion to enemies; scared away the enemies by using skillful tricks and meticulous military tactics; surrounded himself with honest and dignified people and friends, who helped him make right decisions. He magnificently applied meritocracy while punishing duly those who betrayed him and those who betrayed his enemy. These traits were to become a moral core of his essential management.

Style of Genghis Khan's management: Genghis Khan possessed truly humane qualities such as ability to trust and to reward people. As events began to unfold according to his will, these qualities served him as a postulate of communication and as principles of his administration. "Cherish an honest relation" was one of his core principles. He truly cherished the candid behavior and integrity in people and hated scoundrels, traitors with an utmost resolve of punishment. Wherever he was, he always stood for justice and faith. He

scorned fabricators with deceiving character. "The Secret History of the Mongols" tells that all such qualities he demanded from his inner circle and close aides. Genghis Khan considered that a relation without credence is a root of disunity and weakness. Therefore, he punished traitors with cruelest resolve, because he learnt to build any relation on mutual trust and faith. He possessed a fundamental principle of demanding these qualities from his subordinates in order to execute his strategy of administration.

Organization of communication network of administration by Genghis Khan: At that historic era the speed of Mongolian travel was very high compared to other advanced countries, and this became a core element of Genghis Khan's victory and triumph. Kim Jong Reh, a Korean publicist, noted in his book "Historical Figure of the Millennium - Genghis Khan" that "700 years before the invention of Internet, the Mongols created a true network of communication"/page 204/. Thanks to this effective and safe communication network, the Mongol Imperial strategy executed by Genghis was successfully implemented from the Atlantic Ocean to Java Island in the Pacific Ocean, encompassing every part of the Mongolian realm. Everyday activities of the mighty empire were updated and registered by this network. Mongols called it "urtou" or post and its service "yam" and they were constantly supplied with necessary facilities of transportation, workforce, food and etc. Most importantly this network was guarded by specially assigned Mongolian troops to guarantee its functional safety. Messengers of yam rode the best and fastest horses and carried with them "paiza" or token of authority granted by the Great Khan, which allowed them to pass unhindered within the Mongol domain. If messengers failed to deliver a correct message, they were immediately executed as the message itself had an importance of state security. If anyone dared to oppose or hinder "yam", guards duly defended the messenger.

There is a record that in the middle of a fierce battle of Nanjing in Southern China during the Mongol conquest of Sung China a necessary message was delivered within few hours to the Great Khan, who resided in a long distance away from the action. In case of emergency Mongols used fire, smoke and rocket salutes, which had their own messages and signals. Genghis Khan had his own peculiar way of transmitting his thoughts to his people and that was his trance communication with Eternal Blue Sky. After his lucky escape from the Mergid's captivity, he climbed the sacred Mount Burkhan Khaldun - God Hill and pledged to Blue Sky: "Every morning I shall bow thee, pray thee and that You, Great Blue Sky, make descendants of my descendants sensible and moderate!". In the context of Genghis Khan's communication with subordinates, there was a triple symbolization "man-sky-man", which meant he communicated with his people not directly, but through Eternal Blue Sky. Mongols believed that the Sky was a Mighty Power Granter, and accordingly pondered that making good deeds was rewarded by the Sky, whereas bad deeds or sins are chastised by it.

Genghis Khan's methods of reward and gratuity: On the great assembly on the banks of River Onon in

1206 Temujin was crowned as the Great Khan and a sole ruler of the Mongols, and was bestowed a title of Genghis Khan. He decreed to reward those who fought and risked honorably their lives for him and for the state. It was a real meritocracy and he rewarded according to what the person had accomplished. In his decree Genghis inscribed their deeds and achievements so that everyone knew who did what and for what they are rewarded. "The Secret History of the Mongols" delivers many occasions of not only titular and material, but of psychological reward by Genghis Khan. Besides, he could not only punish the people for their mistakes, but pardon them according to the context of his moral postulates. Pardoning was one type of psychological reward. Though many moving facts and evocation by Genghis' close men such as Boorchi, Shikhikhutug, Borokhul, Sorkhanshar and others are described in "The Secret History of the Mongols", it does not tell us in reality that these rewarded individuals constituted an important aspect of Genghis Khan's management methods of gratuity, which he applied in any necessary field. He preferred his subordinates' honesty and desired that in return they had faith in him for his compassion and assistance. On the other hand, he applied a differentiating attitude and high esteem to his rewarding concept. For example, he could gratify any enemy, and that was a unique mastery of administration method, the wise execution of which only he could figure out. "The Secret History of the Mongols" tells that he was a type of leader who could decently estimate, wisely reward and duly gratify and deliver a psychological stimulation and spiritual energy for their achievements to whoever that person was, a humble civilian, an aristocrat, an serf-peasant, a friend and even a foreigner. A system of punishment and emending was an indispensable part of his motivations. That motivational system also pursued a goal of resolving conflicts and contradictions among his subordinates and of defining their guilt and due punishment. In this case their administration rank was seriously taken into consideration. Promotional tempo was obviously slow in Genghis Khan's administration and it demanded huge executive dignity and responsibility. This was a strictly fixed mechanism of the era when subordinates had to submit to the administration style and method of their master. Mongols were proud of their noble origin, and that feeling had developed into nationalism at the time of Genghis Khan, so he exploited it to the outmost.

Authoritarian division by Genghis Khan: Authority and power are essential aspects in the study of Genghis Khan's management style. Foundations of survival and successful existence of any system depend on the delegation of authority and division of powers. Power is a potential force of one's authority to execute something. Without rights and order people cannot achieve their goal. Internecine wars in Mongolia manifested a struggle for power. Power and authority cannot be created out of nothing. They have to be acquired through a long process of human interaction. In reality Genghis Khan's management contained all these theoretical aspects of life. Genghis Khan not only amassed personal power, but centralized it for the entire Great Mongol

Empire. And that is clear for every healthy minded person. As the Mongol Empire gradually grew into a world superpower, Genghis appointed ministers, executives, princes on imperial posts, and defined their nature of duty with truly masterful concept. He clinched to the concept that authority always goes hand in hand not with personality, but with rank. It is a fundamental concept of Genghis Khan's management principle. So far two periods can be identified in the process of Genghis' management:

1. Decentralization and centralization of power. The former involves a period of time before 1206 and the latter encompasses the period after 1206.

2. During the second period a division of authority allows to balance duties, responsibilities, so that Genghis Khan implements a practical work of organization and administration into the realization of huge tasks in the Great Mongol Empire.

Division of authority always involves alterations due to the certain circumstances. In 1206 Genghis appointed ninety-five military commanders for his 1000-men regiments and also decreed Shikhikhutug to lead the State High Court. Various advisers and clerks were appointed in the ministries and for the princes as well. In such way Genghis finally established a common administrative function of "senior to subordinate" system. He strictly forbade misuse of power and corruption. If such betrayal occurred he executed the culprits without any consideration of their background or social origin. Therefore, now or since everyone was equally judged in the face of law and that was to become a golden postulate of the Mongol legislation system and of Genghis Khan's management.

Conclusions

We can make the following conclusions from my research on styles of Genghis Khan's management and economic policy of the Great Mongol Empire:

1. When Genghis Khan and his successors founded the Great Mongol Empire, that encompassed three fourths of the world with superior military tactics and advanced war machine, they never intruded or infringed the internal customs of their conquered nations, only ruled them with a meticulously cautious economic policy by appointing the governing officials and extracting due tributes from them.

2. Genghis Khan was a true master of economics of his era, so that him and his successors created a huge zone of free trade that encompassed all of Eurasia, thus establishing and expanding cultural and civilization ties between the East and the West and created the first ever GATT in the Middle Ages.

3. Distinguished methods of Genghis Khan's management were a postulate of the Mongol Imperial management and a symbol of statecraft, a brief definition of which would be:

"Firstly, amend yourself, then amend your family and lastly, amend your state".

4. Genghis Khan was born a leader whose qualities were instilled in him since his very childhood. He believed that he had a divine destiny for greatness granted to him by the Eternal Blue Sky and its ideals were his strategy of life.

5. Genghis Khan executed a management strategy of internal and external unity of the state.
6. Genghis Khan laid the foundations of style with democratic administration first ever in the world.
7. Study and research of distinguished features of Genghis Khan's management is an invaluable treasure and an eternal subject of debate for the scientists and scholars of the world.

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